

Plan X: moving beyond Plan S to galvanise equitable and open research in the modern era

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Abstract:

Science is a field that is underpinned by research. It is deeply influenced by the prevailing context of the researcher, the funder and academic publishers. Scientific publishing is a costly pursuit with publishing fees, and paywalls exceedingly out of reach for many in resource-constrained settings. Plan S was conceived in 2018; a ground-breaking approach to promote open access to research and facilitate the equitable sharing of ideas. Despite its noble ambitions, it has still fallen short of its goals. It is time to move beyond the pursuit of open-access, to equitable, transparent research in the modern era. It is time to adopt Plan X, a radical approach for *open research* where the power is wrestled back towards our common pursuit of truth.

Plan X proposes the open publication and peer review of research, in what is currently a flourishing network of pre-print servers, with support from publishers, funders and academic institutions to improve the rigour, transparency and efficiency of this system. The cost of publication will simply be the peer-review of another paper, algorithmically matched to your field of expertise, where your contributions to peer review are as important as your contribution to generating research. Plan X continues to see the benefit of academic journals actively pursuing research articles of interest, freely requesting publishing rights to impactful research, reviewed in-house and shared as curated collections in a financial model suited to their objectives and needs.

We call for cOAlition S to adopt Plan X as the next step in their journey. We call on researchers, publishers, academic institutions, funders and the public at-large to join the call for open, transparent and trustworthy publication of research, suited to the modern era through adopting Plan X.

Background:

Science is a field that is underpinned by research. Traditionally, that is the iterative process of hypothesis generation and hypothesis testing in pursuit of the truth. It is seldom linear, and almost always imperfect. It is deeply influenced by the prevailing context of the researcher, and their intellectual milieu. However, in the modern era, it also shaped by the agenda of the funder, and the appetite of the publisher. Impactful academic publishing is a costly pursuit with publishing fees, or 'article processing charges', and paywalls exceedingly out of reach for many in resource-constrained settings.[1] In addition, it is painstakingly slow, with peer review and media embargoes often delaying the impact of important research. In fact, modern academic publishing is far from the transparent and objective pursuit of truth that the public perceive it to be. Instead, it is driven by profit, and not by purpose, obstructing the search for truth.

In light of these problems, Plan S was conceived in 2018; a ground-breaking approach to promote open access to research and facilitate the equitable sharing of ideas. [2] Despite its noble ambitions,

it has still fallen short of its goals. It is time to move beyond the pursuit of open-access, to equitable, transparent research in the modern era. It is time to adopt Plan X, a radical approach for *open research* where the power is wrestled back towards our common pursuit of truth.

Main Text:

Science is the pursuit of a common truth, where scientists work together to find answers to life's most pressing questions. This is not always as straightforward as one might think. Rather, it is a dynamic and complex process, fraught with controversy and clashes. One truth today might be turned on its head tomorrow, and one that was thrown out yesterday might become the new standard tomorrow.[3] That is if we can all agree. And agree we must if the public are to believe in the truth. This is where the realm of peer-reviewed academic publishing was born. We needed to ensure that the research we were conducting was rigorous and accurate, and that our peers agreed with our methods and our conclusions. For a scientist's real purpose is to share their research with others, and to be confident that what they are sharing is the truth.

One can't imagine which researchers thought the best way to do this was to pay large sums of money to publishers, for someone to decide whether your work was worthy of sharing; if the odds were in your favour, that the peers they selected happened to agree with you; then, to keep that research hidden behind paywalls, lest someone with fewer resources wish to read your work. The field of academic publishing is riddled with delays, exorbitant costs, difficulty in obtaining rigorous peer review and ever pervasive poor-quality and even manipulated or falsified research. These barriers have driven the emergence of so-called 'pirate journals' which charge exorbitant publishing fees, for guaranteed publishing of manuscripts. This is positioned against the backdrop of increasing growth in publication outputs globally, where rigorous peer-review is facing increasing scrutiny. The pool of expert reviewers is limited, and time-constraints contribute to editors' struggles to get quality reviews of submitted manuscripts, compounding a delay in publishing. Even peer-review itself is from infallible, with many articles retracted after publishing. [4]

Plan X was conceived after being deeply unsettled by the pervasive culture of academic publishing, fraught with delays, elitism, and costly fees. The more we allow the power of sharing of research to rest in the hands of the few, typically in the global north, the more we compound inequities in research, and stifle accurate, timely, and impactful research that is both open, and honest. It is on this background, that cOAlition S pioneered open-access research in 2018, and in 2023, released their call for a radical new approach to academic publishing.[5] It was clear that the field was in dire need of a publishing model designed by researchers, for researchers to promote the rapid, equitable and transparent dissemination of rigorous, high-quality research. To achieve this, buy-in from researchers, academic institutions, and funders is critical.

What would the ideal research environment look like if we started from scratch? Opinions differ, but perhaps we should examine it from all angles? For a researcher, it would be an equitable environment driven by the research, and those conducting it, funding it, and using it. An environment where rigorous, living research is able to be rapidly and openly shared with the field, and the public. To the publishers, it would be an environment where good-quality, critically appraised impactful research is available to share through curated platforms with the broader academic community. To the public, it would be research that is accessible, trustworthy and transparent. Policymakers would likely have a similar perspective, ensuring easier and faster translation into practice, while not sacrificing on scientific rigour. Are these desires mutually exclusive? No. It is time to move beyond *open-access* research, and embrace *open* research, that is

guided by the principles of transparency, fairness, and equity towards the pursuit of a common truth for the benefit of all stakeholders.

Plan X proposes the open publication and peer-review of research, in what is currently a flourishing network of pre-print servers. We propose a package of services that open research platforms should provide when becoming signatories to Plan X. These pre-print servers should contain room for comment by approved authors, and publicly show reservations and rebuttals of experts in the field by requiring three independent peer-reviews from experts in the field before achieving a 'peer-reviewed' badge. To achieve this, funders and academic institutions should become signatories to Plan X. Rather than it being a prerequisite that research is published in an academic journal, it should be a prerequisite that the researcher publishes on an open-research server, and when doing so, reviews a paper in the same field. The cost of your submission is quite simply a peer-review of another article by up to three of your authors. Scientific accomplishment should be measured not only by published work, but by the equally important dedication to *open research* and peer-review in your field. Verification of academic standing will be incorporated through partnerships with academic institutions. Advances in machine learning allow for the accurate matching of expertise, improving the quality of the peer-review process. Funders should include peer-review as part of the funding mandate, and academic institutions should incorporate into conditions of tenure, ensuring ongoing upliftment of scientific fields.

In this environment, where does this leave scientific publishers? This doesn't negate the need for journals, whose editors are free to peruse the open-research servers and conferences and invite authors to allow them to share their work in their journals—much like a newspaper may obtain permission to share an article, and in keeping with current practices of journal editors today. They can use in-house field experts and methodologists to provide rigorous and consistent scientific review, before selecting impactful articles related to their field for curated publishing. This allows readers of the journal to be exposed to articles which the editors feel are impactful and are of broad interest, knowing that they have passed stringent tests serving their original purpose more faithfully. For these efforts, they can continue to choose a financing-model that fits their needs and objectives, without compromising *open research*. How do we prevent elitism and bias from encroaching on this process? Plan X proposed an open equity metric, where journals are measured by their commitment to equitable publishing across various spheres, including authors themselves to the regions they represent and the findings of their research. This would continue the tradition of journals sharing important work, keep the prestige of high-impact journal publishing, but remove the pressure to submit, pay significant fees and embargo the research until publication while maintaining, and even improving the rigour, and trustworthiness of research.

Conclusion:

It is time to move beyond open-access research, and embrace *open research*, that is guided by the principles of transparency, fairness and equity towards the pursuit of a common truth. Plan X calls on cOAlition S to adopt Plan X as the next step, with support and co-development from funders, academic institutions and publishers. Join the call, and ask cOAlition S to support Plan X to *open research*.

List of Abbreviations:

None

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Declarations

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Not applicable

Consent for publication

Not applicable

Availability of data and materials

Not applicable

Conflict of Interest

XX is an early-career researcher who has: submitted to and been rejected from multiple prestigious journals; paid exorbitant fees to publish work; has been subjected to media embargoes; and has been denied access to others' work by paywalls.

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Authors' contributions:

XX conceived the manuscript, was responsible for writing, reviewing and has approved the final draft.